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Exploring Management Methods Employed In Managing Stadiums In South-South Nigeria

Inipami Prince Johnnie¹ & Anthony Obiosa²

¹Department Of Quantity Surveying,
Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
johnniepami@yahoo.com

²Rivers State Ministry of Lands and Survey
Point Block, Secretariat Complex, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria
obiosatony@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The present paper is on exploring management methods employed in managing stadiums in south-south Nigeria. The study utilized the descriptive research design. The population for the study covered the staff (both full time and part time) that performed different functions and roles in the case study stadiums across the study areas. The population across the three-case study stadiums was at one thousand four hundred (1400) staff (full time and part time staff). The researcher carried out a face-to-face questionnaire administration to the respondents in the selected stadiums. The researcher solicited for the assistance of the facility manager to assist him in informing the staff and administer the questionnaires to them. Both quantitative and qualitative methods were employed in the data analysis. For quantitative aspects; Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and excel, frequency distributions, percentages and descriptive analysis of the safety measures in managing stadiums. Data collected was collated and analyzed using various quantitative statistical models such as bar chart and pie chart. Each data was examined and analyzed on its merit and grouped into the various aspects of information requirement for the purpose of this research work. The findings were critically examined again to make sure that they are not incongruous with the research objectives. Mean and the standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions posed for the study. A mean score of 2.50 was the benchmark for acceptance. The findings showed that the government owns and controls the day to day running of the case study stadiums and its facilities, and that there were no instituted bodies responsible to regulate and monitor stadium safety and its facilities. it was recommended among others that safety guide that would regulate sports facilities should be published.

Keywords: managing stadiums, management methods

INTRODUCTION

Stadiums have played host to a lot of games, sports activities and events. Some stadiums are purpose-built to suit particular sporting needs, i.e. Olympic Games; Federation of International Football Association (FIFA) World Cup, while others are built generally for multipurpose use. Linsi (2007) states that the first age of football stadiums were constructed between 1890s and 1930s; these were done as a result of the football game gaining more recognition and becoming more popular. Plate 1.1 shows an example of the first football stadiums built. The second age of stadium construction began in 1980s. In the 1980s, need for an increase of stadia and capacity to host this game became very necessary then. However, most of

these designs gave little or no attention to safety, user satisfaction and convenience of spectators, as a result of that, many incidents resulting to several tragedies have being recorded in the sports facilities. These include gang violence, collapse of stadium, power failure, stampede etc. In the developed countries, there have been several challenges encountered in the use of stadium; in England for example, most notable is the Hillsborough disaster that occurred on the 15th April 1989, at the Hillsborough Stadium in Sheffield, during the Football Association (FA Cup) semifinal match between Liverpool and Nottingham Forest football clubs. A crush in the incidence resulted to the death of about ninety six (96) people and injuries to seven hundred and sixty six (766) others (BBC news 2016). Another case was the collapse of a section of a stadium in Bekal, India (Dec 2013) during a football match which more than 100 people were believed to have been injured, when an entire football stand collapsed before a football match in India. The shocking incident happened minutes before the start of a match between Saban Kottakkal and Mohammadans Mouval while a boy juggled a football out on the pitch at the Bekal Brothers Sports Club. Around one thousand five hundred (1,500) people were thought to have been on ground, as the stand, which was reportedly made up of wooden planks and iron rods, collapsed. Initial reports suggested that a heavy rain was the cause of the collapse. it made the wood moist, leaving it weak and unable to hold the weight of the spectators.

The first stadiums to be built in the modern era were basic facilities, designed for the single purpose of fitting as many spectators in as possible. With tremendous growth in the popularity of organised sport in the late Victorian era, especially association football in the United Kingdom and baseball in the United States, the first such structures were built.^[10] One such early stadium was the Lansdowne Road Stadium, the brainchild of Henry Dunlop, who organised the first All Ireland Athletics Championships. Banned from locating sporting events at Trinity College, Dunlop built the stadium in 1872. "I laid down a cinder running path of a quarter-mile, laid down the present Lansdowne Tennis Club ground with my own theodolite, started a Lansdowne archery club, a Lansdowne cricket club, and last, but not least, the Lansdowne Rugby Football Club – colours red, black and yellow." Some 300 cartloads of soil from a trench beneath the railway were used to raise the ground, allowing Dunlop to use his engineering expertise to create a pitch envied around Ireland. Other early stadiums from this period in the UK include the Stamford Bridge stadium (opened in 1877 for the London Athletic Club) and Anfield stadium (1884 as a venue for Everton F.C.). The South End Grounds (*pictured in 1893*) was one of the first-generation "wooden ballparks". In the U.S., many professional baseball teams built large stadiums mainly out of wood, with the first such venue being the South End Grounds in Boston, opened in 1871 for the team then known as the Boston Beaneaters (now the Atlanta Braves). Many of these parks caught fire, and those that did not proved inadequate for a growing game. All of the 19th-century wooden parks were replaced, some after a few years, and none survive today.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

To explore the management methods employed in managing stadiums in South-South Nigeria.

Research Question

What are the various methods employed in managing stadiums in Nigeria?

Significance of the Study

The several incidents from various stadiums in Nigeria which has caused the untimely death of so many persons, and brought pain to several families in Nigeria, have shown that there is a need to call for a state of emergency in stadium management. With several states, constructing 'state of the art' stadiums, but lacking the professional know-how on how to run these facilities, has informed the choice of study.

Scope of the Study

The scope of this study will be limited to stadiums in South-South, Nigeria (Rivers State, Akwa Ibom State and Delta State). These stadiums were newly constructed in the twenty first century, and therefore form the basis for consideration and selection as a case study. They have often been used as host to the National team of Nigeria (Super Eagles) when they play their matches. The case study stadiums are

- i. Adokiye Amiesimaka stadium Omagwa, Rivers State
- ii. Godswill Akpabio Stadium Uyo, Akwa Ibom State
- iii. Stephen Keshi Stadium Asaba. Delta State.

Safety

The degree of luxury, comfort and convenience which can be built into a stadium will depend on the amount of funds available. However, the fundamental requirement which must be met, regardless of available funding levels, is that the stadium must be a safe and secure facility for all those who use it, whether they are spectators, match participants, officials, media personnel, staff or others. Even before the basic planning begins, safety in the stadium should be uppermost. It should be clearly understood by the prospective owners and by those concerned in the planning, designing, construction and management processes that human safety will be the first and foremost priority. It will be a condition that may not, under any circumstances, be put aside or circumvented in order to accommodate other requirements. Safety measures or intervention has been defined as an attempt to change how things are done in order to improve safety (Okoye P.U, Okolie K.C, and Ngwu C 2017). Safety interventions (which entail a number of activities) are resourceful tools in the control or prevention of workplace accidents.

Specific Safety Requirements

In looking at safety in stadium management, there has to be safety legislations to be considered as templates in measuring or monitoring performances. These templates stand as a guide in safety as regards to stadium management. In this study; three evaluating templates have been employed, they are

- i. FIFA Technical Report 2007 (FIFA TRR 2007),
- ii. League Management Company (2014/2015 Criteria for Stadium Inspection and Certification) appendix B.
- iii. Guide to Safety at Sports Ground 2008 (The Green Book).

These templates will be used to explain and x-ray general safety in stadium management, design of a stadium and its facilities and management responsibility for safety.

Structural safety

Although, building and safety standards and requirements vary from country to country but it is essential that, within the relevant framework, the most stringent safety standards are applied. Every aspect of the stadium's structure must be approved and certified by the relevant building and safety authorities in the locality *FIFA, TRR (2007)*.

Fire prevention

This is an integral part of safety measures, it must be ensured that all fire-fighting facilities in the every stadium has to be of standard and the fire precautions must be certified and approved by the relevant local fire authorities, as must the fire safety standards of all parts of the stadium. *FIFA, TRR (2007)*.

Stadium control room

The measuring template recommends that each stadium must have a control room which has an overall view of the inside of the stadium and which must be equipped with public address facilities and television surveillance monitor screens. The size, configuration and furnishing of the control room should be agreed upon in consultation with the local police. The stadium commander or safety manager as the case may be, should have the capability of overriding and cutting into the public address system whenever necessary. The system governing the arrest, detention and indictment of offenders may differ from country to country, or even from city to city, so stadium designers should consult the local police and civic authorities to determine whether it is necessary to include facilities such as a police muster room, a charge room and detention cells for male and female prisoners within the stadium itself. A second control room and emergency command centre is desirable. It should have a location which is convenient for arriving emergency personnel and their vehicles. *FIFA, TRR (2007)*.

Television surveillance system

A modern stadium should be equipped inside and outside with public surveillance colour television cameras, mounted in fixed positions with pan and tilt facilities. These cameras should monitor all of the stadium's approaches and all of the public areas inside and outside the stadium. The television surveillance system should have its own independent power supply and private circuit. It should be operated and controlled from the stadium control room where the monitor screens should be situated. It should be capable of taking still photographs both inside and outside the stadium. *FIFA, TRR (2007)*.

First aid rooms for the public

There is also provision for first aid rooms. Every stadium should be equipped with a first aid room, or rooms, to care for spectators. Ideally, there should be two first aid rooms, one on either side of the stadium, but the number, size and location of these rooms should be agreed in consultation with the local health authorities. There should be space for the secure deposit of defibrillators in easily accessible locations, evenly distributed around the stadium. Scenarios for dealing with a mass catastrophe are a joint venture of the local authorities and the stadium management. *FIFA, TRR (2007)*.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilized the descriptive research design. Rivers State, also known simply as Rivers, is one of the 36 states of Nigeria. Rivers state currently has three stadiums (Sharks Stadium located at Port Harcourt township metropolis, Yakubu Gowon Stadium located at Elekahia and AdokiyeAmiesimaka Stadium located at Omagwa. Akwa Ibom is a state in Nigeria. It is located in the coastal southern part of the country, lying between latitudes 4°32'N and 5°33'N, and longitudes 7°25'E and 8°25'E. The state is located in the South-South geopolitical zone, and is bordered on the east by Cross River State, on the west by Rivers State and Abia State, and on the south by the Atlantic Ocean and the southernmost tip of Cross River State. Delta State (created on August 27, 1991) is an oil and agricultural producing state in Nigeria. It is situated in the region known as the South-South geo-political zone with a population of 4,112,445. The capital city is Asaba, located at the northern end of the state, with an estimated area of 762 square kilometres (294 sq mi), while Warri is the economic nerve center of the state and also the most populated. It is located in the southern end of the state. The population for the study covered the staff (both full time and part time) that performed different functions and roles in the case study stadiums across the study areas. The population across the three-case study stadiums was at one thousand four hundred (1400) staff (full time and part time staff). Using large samples from different stadiums (Public and Private) would have been appropriate for this research, but because of insufficient funds and the security challenges in the country, I have narrowed it down to three (3) case studies. This will in no form reduce the quality of the research as the case studies tend to provide answers to the research questions and could also stand as a standard in stadium management. Researchers require academic and professional experts to edit their questionnaires before a survey can be carried out (Umeh, 2018). According to Devellis as cited by Mugenda, (2004) reliability is the proportion of variance attributable to the time measurement of a variable and estimates the consistency of such measurement over time from a research instrument. It is a measure of the degree to which a research instrument would yield the same results or data after repeated trials. The researcher carried out a face-to-face questionnaire administration to the respondents in the selected stadiums. The researcher solicited for the assistance of the facility manager to assist him in informing the staff and administer the questionnaires to them. Both quantitative and qualitative methods were employed in the data analysis. For quantitative aspects; Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and excel, frequency distributions, percentages and descriptive analysis of the safety measures in managing stadiums. Data collected was collated and analyzed using various quantitative statistical models such as bar chart and pie chart. Each data was examined and analyzed on its merit and grouped into the various aspects of information requirement for the purpose of this research work. The findings were critically examined again to make sure that they are not incongruous with the research objectives. Mean and the standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions posed for the study. A mean score of 2.50 was the benchmark for acceptance.

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria Showing South- South
Source: Department of Surveying and Geoinformatics, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka, (2019)

Figure 2: Map of South- South Showing the Study Areas
Source: Department of Surveying and Geoinformatics, NnamdiAzikiwe University, Awka, 2019

Sources of Data

Guest *et al.* (2013) define a source as a person or event that provides primary data for any study. For this study, both primary and secondary sources of data were consulted. Primary source of data was a

structured questionnaire constructed by the researcher to elicit responses from the respondents in the study. Secondary sources include some published pieces of work by renowned scholars and educators. Nicholas (2014) defines secondary data as that which has been interpreted and recorded

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Data Presentation

Distribution of Questionnaires

Out of the three hundred and eleven (311) questionnaire links shared across the three case study stadium locations, only three hundred and six (306) were fit for data analysis. The breakdown of the questionnaire distribution is shown in figure 4.1 below. AdokiyeAmiesimaka Stadium had a total of 105 (34.3%) respondents, GodswillAkpabio Stadium had a total of 104 (34%) respondents while Stephen Keshi stadium had a total of 97 (31.7%) respondents.

Figure3: Questionnaire Distribution Across the Case Study

Research Question: What are the various methods employed to manage stadiums in Nigeria?

In the study, the government owns and controls the day to day running of the case study stadiums and its facilities. For instance, in GodswillAkpabio international stadium, the AkwaIbom State government under Ministry of Sport and Youth Development handles the day to day running of the stadium and its facilities while the maintenance of the facility was outsourced to Julius Berger PLC, who oversees the statutory and routine maintenance of the stadium. The firm presents yearly maintenance budget to the state government where it is added to the state budget under recurrent expenses in the Ministry of Sport and Youth Development. Similarly, at Adokiye Amiesimaka Stadium, the day to day running of the stadium and its facilities is being done by the Ministry of Sports but the maintenance of the facility is outsourced to CICO Deux Nigeria Ltd. CICO Deux Nigeria Ltd is saddled with the responsibility of carrying out both statutory and routine maintenance of the stadium. They present their yearly budget for the maintenance to the State Government through the Ministry of Sports who adds the budget to the Ministry’s budget under the recurrent expenses and present same to the State Government. However, at Stephen Keshi stadium in Delta state under the Delta Sports Commission undertakes the running the day to day activities of the stadium and its facilities along with the maintenance of the facilities. The Delta Sport Commission executes all the maintenance needs of the stadium ranging from the statutory to routine maintenance. They also present yearly budget of the Commission where the maintenance budget for the stadium is duly captured. While government of each of these States, categorically make the maintenance policy and provide the budgetary allocations for the maintenance of the stadium and its facilities, the

outsourcing firms schedules and carryout the routine maintenance of the stadium and its facilities in accordance to the maintenance policy of the state government.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

On the various methods employed to manage stadiums in Nigeria, findings showed that the government owns and controls the day to day running of the case study stadiums and its facilities, and that there were no instituted bodies responsible to regulate and monitor stadium safety and its facilities. However, safety inspections were done whenever the facility was to be put in use. The safety inspection teams were mostly comprised of perceived professionals from the organisation requesting to use the stadium facilities. These team of persons most times do not have the necessary safety qualifications to understand what safety measures must be put in place before the facility can be used. These inspections are not usually wholistic as minor safety issues are sometimes overlooked because the venue has already been selected for the event. In cases where the facility is to be used for an international event such as FIFA football match, etc. the safety inspections carried out by the international organisation ensures strict compliance to international stadium safety standard but when a local event such as musical concerts, recruitment exams, religious programs etc. is to be hosted at such stadium, the safety inspections are not usually the same as those for international events.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study was on the examination of the safety measures in the management of stadium facilities in the south-south Nigeria, using three case study stadiums which were Godswill Akpabio stadium at AkwaIbom State, Adokiye Amiesimaka Stadium at Rivers State and Stephen Keshi stadium at Delta State. A research objective and question were stated for the study. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study included both full-time and part-time staff of the case study stadiums. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size of the study where a total of 311 respondents were sampled randomly from a population of 1400 persons. The instrument for data collection was a structured 4-likert point questionnaire with a semi structured interview guide. Data analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20 and 2016 Microsoft Excel. The analysis was done using frequency distributions, percentages and descriptive analysis of safety indicators as a tool in managing stadiums. Mean and the standard deviation were used to analyze the research questions posed for the study. A mean score of 2.50 was the benchmark for acceptance. Findings showed that the safety measures available in each stadium were adequate but the method of administering and managing these measures were not reliable. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that there is no constituted institution or organization to regulate and monitor safety of stadiums and its facilities.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researcher made the following recommendations for the study;

1. A safety guide that would regulate sports facilities should be published.
2. Institutions that should be responsible for the regulating and monitoring of safety of stadiums and its facilities should be set up.
3. The use of electronics counting turnstile gates should be mandatory for all stadiums in South-South, Nigeria to ensure capacity control.

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